

Table 2. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon under various fertilizer treatments.

Treatment	1994		1995		1996		Av	
	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon
1/2 of N	5.4	1.2	6.2	2.3	4.9	2.2	5.5	1.9
1/4 of N	5.1	1.2	6.5	2.4	4.7	2.3	5.4	2.0
1/2 of NPK	5.2	1.3	6.2	2.4	6.0	2.5	5.8	2.1
1/2 of NK	5.4	1.4	6.4	2.7	6.2	2.1	6.0	2.0
1/2 of NP	5.6	1.4	6.4	2.5	6.1	2.2	6.0	2.0
No fertilizer	5.2	1.2	6.5	2.3	6.0	1.8	5.9	1.8
CV (%)	–	17.1	–	7.2	–	8.7	–	9.9
F test	–	ns	–	ns	–	^a	–	^a

^aSignificant at $P < 0.05$. ns = not significant..

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Rooting inhibitors in soil solution under an intensive rice-cropping system

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The productivity of double- and triple-rice cropping conducted at IRRI over the last 30 years has been shown to be declining (Cassman et al 1995). Although extensive studies on various aspects such as soil nutrient supply, deficiency and/or toxicity of nutrients, and climate change over time have been carried out to identify the causes, the phenomenon has not been fully understood. Some toxic substances, accumulated under anaerobic conditions after amendment of plant residues, have been reported to inhibit root elongation (Tanaka et al 1990). Appropriate development and function of root systems are essential for satisfactory yield performance of the crop. This study was conducted to determine the presence of a rooting inhibitor in a soil solution collected from IRRI fields subjected to intensive rice cropping.

Soil samples were collected from 0- to 30-cm depths in fertilized plots under the long-term continuous cropping experiment (LTCCE) and long-term fertility experiment (LTFE) at IRRI (see table). A soil solution (500 mL) was extracted using a centrifuge (560 g for 10 min at 20 °C) and its pH adjusted to 3.5. The soil solu-

tion was loaded in 5 g of Amberlite XAD-8. The column was eluted with 50% ethanol, 100% ethanol, and chloroform for crude fractionation of substances according to water solubility. These three fractions were completely evaporated in vacuo at 40 °C and dissolved in 25 mL of phosphate buffer (66.7 mM at pH 6.8). Dehusked seeds of IR72 were pregerminated in the dark at 30 °C; seedlings with 5-mm-long radicles were then selected for bioassay. Ten seedlings were placed into a 50-mL beaker containing 5 mL of the test solution. Radicle lengths were measured 72 h after incubation in the dark at 30 °C. A set of seedlings was incubated with phosphate buffer only and used as the control. All measurements were made with five replications.

In the LTCCE, radicle elongation

was moderately inhibited in each fraction (see figure). The elongation was least in the 100% ethanol fraction. In the LTFE, the chloroform fraction, which contains the least water-soluble substances, showed drastic inhibitory effects, reducing the elongation to less than 20% of the control. Results suggest the presence of some rooting inhibitors in the soil solution of LTCCE and LTFE plots at IRRI. Tanaka et al (1990) reported inhibitory effects on rice root elongation in the ether fraction. This fraction is identical to the chloroform fraction in this study, from rice soil amended with wheat straw. Major substances in the fraction were identified as two aromatic acids, 2-phenylpropionic acid and 3-phenylpropionic acid. The inhibitory effect was greater in LTFE plots

Sampling date of soils and management of fields under long-term continuous cropping experiment (LTCCE) and long-term fertility experiment (LTFE), IRRI, Philippines.

Site	Sampling date	Cropping frequency	Residue management	Water management
LTCCE	14 DBT ^a	3 times y ⁻¹	Remove	Irrigated year-round
LTFE	21 DAT ^b	2 times y ⁻¹	Incorporate	Irrigated year-round

^aDays before transplanting, 1999 dry season. ^bDays after transplanting, 1999 dry season.

Inhibitory effects of the soil solution on radicle elongation of IR72, LTCCE and LTFE, IRRI.

into which plant residues have been incorporated after every harvest than in LTCCE plots from where residues have been removed. Thus, it is assumed that inhibitory substances in the chloroform fraction may be derived from plant residues.

The concentration of the test solution applied for bioassay was 20 times that of the original. Hence, it should be further confirmed whether the growth and yield of rice plants in LTCCE and LTFE plots are directly affected through root development by those substances under practical conditions. The chemical identification of the substances, especially in the chloro-

form fraction, is the subject of another study.

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Yield response of different rice varieties to root damage at the heading stage

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Root systems play an important role in the absorption and storage of water and nutrients and in the synthesis of certain hormones. Root cutting may increase the growth and yield of rice because the soil disturbance resulting from root cutting has some beneficial effect on soil conditions, or excess root production may reduce shoot growth because it competes for carbohydrates. Moreover, differences among soils, varieties, and management systems exist. To determine whether a large root system is beneficial to yield, we conducted a field experiment on the effect of root cutting at the heading stage in Guangzhou, China, in 1998. The soil was a clay loam, fertilized with 150 kg N, 33 kg P, and 124.5 kg K ha⁻¹. Five varieties were grown in the early-season and late-season experiments: Guang-Lu-Ai (short stalk) and Er-Qing-Ai (tall stalk) for the early season (March–July); Pei-Za 72 (hybrid rice), Feng-Ai Zhan 1, and Te-San-Ai for the late season (July–November).

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing at two seedlings hill⁻¹. The root systems of treated blocks were vertically cut 1 cm away from the stalk to a 20-cm depth on one, two, or three sides of the plant (T₁, T₂, T₃, respectively) at the heading stage. No cutting was done in the control variety (check). Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Block size was 15 m². Root activity was measured in terms of α-naphthylamine-oxidizing activities with a spectrometer. Yield and yield components were analyzed and recorded at maturity.

Table 1 shows that root cutting at the heading stage significantly increased root activity at the ripening stage in general, irrespective of varieties and treatments. The remaining roots evidently compensated for the ones removed.

In Table 2, one-side cutting (T₁) increased yield in four varieties (Guang-Lu-Ai, 10.2%; Pei-Za 72, 4.6%; Feng-Ai Zhan 1, 12.8%; and Te-San-Ai, 11.4%) and decreased yield in one (Er-Qing-Ai, 18.2%). The difference was mainly associated with a difference in grains panicle⁻¹ and percentage filled grains. Two-side cutting (T₂) and three-side cutting (T₃) caused

Table 1. Effect of root cutting at heading stage on root activity (μg α-NA g⁻¹ DW h⁻¹).

Treatment	Variety ^a				
	Guang-Lu-Ai	Er-Qing-Ai	Pei-Za 72	Feng-Ai Zhan I	Te-San-Ai
Check	43.7 b	87.5 b	96.4 c	59.2 b	84.2 b
T ₁	48.3 b	111.8 a	108.2 b	73.4 a	89.3 ab
T ₂	111.4 a	109.9 a	123.5 a	70.2 a	93.4 a
T ₃	101.7 a	102.3 a	109.5 b	68.4 a	90.5 a

^aNumbers followed by different letters in a column significantly differ at P = 0.05.